

Resolution Booklet

2nd Small Scale Event for University Students

MOTION FOR A RESOLUTION BY
THE COMMITTEE ON TRANSPORT AND TOURISM

The Tourist: Extended travel restrictions due to COVID-19 have brought the tourism sector to a global pause, resulting in unprecedented revenue losses for the tourism businesses.

Taking into account that, prior to the pandemic, the growth of mass tourism had been negatively impacting Europe's top travel destinations, how can the EU support Member States in rebuilding their tourism industry, while promoting sustainability?

Submitted by: Beatriz Almeida (PT), Maria Sá (PT), Patrícia Curado (PT), Petar Rajković (Chairperson, RS), Sofia Cruz (Chairperson, PT)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Aware that the tourism industry accounts for [26 million jobs in the EU](#),
- B. Deeply concerned by the fact that [travelling facilitates the spread](#) of the Covid-19 virus,
- C. Acknowledging the [communities whose GDP mostly depend on revenue](#) from the tourism sector,
- D. Reaffirming the potential of the [digitalisation of travel](#),
- E. Alarmed by the [unsustainability of the tourism sector](#) regarding:
 - i) the damage to the natural environment,
 - ii) the high levels of carbon emissions that result from the frequent and increased use of cars, trains, and airplanes,
 - iii) the commodification of culture,
 - iv) the decline of living standards of local residents,
- F. Emphasising the need to adapt tourists' [travel tendencies from before the Covid-19 pandemic](#), with more conscious and deliberate choices,
- G. Contemplating the [newest travel trends](#), such as:
 - i) short-haul travel within citizens' own countries,
 - ii) longer vacation periods, where citizens can combine leisure and work,
 - iii) trips that allow respectful and safe engagement with the local communities;

1. Invites Member States to further invest in the education of citizens who are employed in the tourism sector;
2. Endorses Member States to continue investing in measures and regulations that fight the spread of the coronavirus by:
 - a) continuing the mandatory implementation of negative PCR tests for people crossing state borders;
 - b) implementing periodic testing of workers in the tourism industry;
3. Calls upon the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation ([DG RTD](#)) to promote digitalisation by continuing to provide monetary incentives for innovation in the field of tourism;
4. Encourages Member States to lower their respective carbon footprint by investing in environmentally-friendly public transportation options;
5. Suggests the Directorate-General for the Environment ([DG ENV](#)) to support environmental tourism by funding the creation of natural parks and reserves;
6. Invites Member States to support the digitalisation of the arts field by organising live streams of musical and theatrical performances;
7. Recommends Member States to support the development of eco-tourism through subsidies;
8. Further encourages Member States to establish detailed legislation for employees working from home.

MOTION FOR A RESOLUTION BY
THE COMMITTEE ON CIVIL LIBERTIES, JUSTICE AND HOME AFFAIRS

Not modern, just a family: Taking into consideration the varying national laws on same-sex marriage and adoption and the gap in the recognition of these families between Member-States, what course of action should the EU follow to ensure consistent family rights in its jurisdiction?

Submitted by: Mariana Filipa Valente Duarte (PT), Teresa Lourenço de Almeida Lucas Serra (PT), Kostiantyn Varvaryk (Chairperson, UA)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Keeping in mind that Article 9 of [the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU](#) consolidates the right to marry and found a family, in accordance with national law,
- B. Noting with regret that only [13 out of 27](#) Member States fully recognise same-sex marriage and adoption,
- C. Noting with concern that social acceptance of same-sex marriage and adoption, in most of the countries that do not recognise them, [is lower than 40%](#),
- D. Emphasising that the rights of same-sex couples should be promoted and protected across the EU,
- E. Aware of the differences in current legislation regarding same-sex marriage and adoption among Member States,
- F. Concerned that variations in recognition of same-sex marriages and adoption hinder LGBTQI+ people's right to freedom of movement,
- G. Affirming the [European Parliament Resolution](#) on the Declaration of the EU as an LGBTIQ Freedom Zone,
- H. Taking into account [the European Commission initiative](#) on cross-border recognition of parenthood;

1. Calls upon the European Commission to actively advocate for equality in same-sex marriages and adoption rights by supporting local Human Rights activists;
2. Urges Member States to harmonise legislation on same-sex marriages and adoption rights;
3. Encourages Member States to adapt educational curricula by including information on different gender identities and sexual orientations;
4. Asks Non-Governmental Organisations to continue their actions for the recognition of same-sex marriage and adoption rights;
5. Hopes that all Member States widely recognise same-sex marriages and adoption procedures established in other Member States;
6. Reminds Member States to comply with the European Parliament Resolution on the Declaration of the EU as an LGBTIQ Freedom Zone;
7. Invites the European Commission to secure that the Initiative on cross-border recognition of parenthood is also applicable to same-sex parenthood.

**MOTION FOR A RESOLUTION BY
THE COMMITTEE ON INTERNAL MARKET AND CONSUMER PROTECTION**

Not a Game: The video game industry has overtaken film as the largest entertainment industry in the world, with 2.3 billion gamers globally. This boom is in part due to the growth of randomised in-game purchases and excessive monetisation. What can Europe do to protect both children and adults from abusive and addictive mechanics which blur the lines between gambling and gaming?

Submitted by: Alexandra Nobre (PT), Ana Luísa (PT), Dimitrios Chatzis (GR), Maria Eduarda Leite (Chairperson, PT)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Concerned with the [lack of regulation](#) around addictive practices in video games,
 - B. Emphasising the existence of unregulated gambling-like activities related to loot box openings, trading and skin betting,
 - C. Pointing out the insufficient research and lack of data about the relation between gaming and gambling,
 - D. Noting with concern that games containing microtransactions targeted at adults are also easily available for, and played by, children,
 - E. Alarmed that [60%](#) of the top mobile games on Google Play and Apple's App Store contain loot boxes, [over 90%](#) of them are rated as suitable for children aged 12+,
 - F. Taking into account the gaming industry's [unwillingness to acknowledge](#) the existence of problematic design features that promote addiction;
-
- 1. Invites gaming companies to include in the labels of their games:
 - a) the monetisation strategies used,
 - b) the medical problems related to game usage;
 - 2. Encourages Member States to study the effects of the regulations implemented in [Belgium and the Netherlands](#) against loot boxes;

3. Suggests the European Commission harmonises the definition and types of gambling;
4. Calls upon the European Commission to create research grants for:
 - a) improving parental supervision tools,
 - b) identifying the addictive effects of loot boxes on players;
5. Requests the European Commission to protect children from the effects of gambling in the gaming context by introducing monetisation warnings in the [PEGI label](#);
6. Further invites gaming companies to create online databases of their gamers' activity, under the General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#));
7. Further suggests the European Commission to cooperate with the gaming industry towards establishing common monetisation systems.

**MOTION FOR A RESOLUTION BY
THE COMMITTEE ON CULTURE AND EDUCATION**

Good Luck Charlie: Since 1990, children have become less able to produce unique and unconventional ideas. In a generation where innovation and entrepreneurship are the keys to future development, how should the EU foster innovation in the workforce, while also promoting creativity inside its educational systems?

Submitted by: Beatriz Bastos (PT), Joana Belo (PT), João Ferreira (PT), Rodrigo Simões (PT)
Inês Rodrigues (Chairperson, PT)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Conscious that [creativity is as important in today's world education as literacy](#),
- B. Gravely concerned that since the 1990s there has been a [decrease in creative and original thinking](#) among children,
- C. Acknowledging that [95% of respondents](#) of the *Digital Education Action Plan* consultation consider the COVID-19 crisis to be a turning point for digital technologies in education,
- D. Noting that [rigid and restrictive national curricula](#) fails to stimulate creativity and curiosity in students,
- E. Fully aware that [standardised testing increases stress levels](#) and burnout in children,
- F. Reaffirming the value of the education workforce as one of the most important [levers for change](#),
- G. Emphasising the need to [adapt school systems to the market demand skills](#) in a world of constant and rapid change,
- H. Considering that [the current school systems fail to prioritise creativity](#);

1. Requests the [Media Convergence and Social Media Unit](#) of the European Commission to promote media campaigns, incentivising creative endeavours and recognising creative individuals;
2. Encourages the [Directorate-General for Education and Culture](#) to create a committee with the aim of:
 - a. researching and promoting technological and non-technological ways of amusement,
 - b. recognising the dangers of screen addiction;
3. Suggests the European Commission promotes workshops on the development of digital skills for students and teachers under the [Digital Education Action Plan](#);
4. Invites Member States to reform their national educational curricula by:
 - a. allowing for more didactic and flexible courses at advanced stages of education,
 - b. renewing and reshaping the existing course contents;
5. Proposes the European Commission to establish a partnership with [Mental Health Europe](#) aimed at researching students' mental health during school years;
6. Calls upon the European Institute of Innovation and Technology ([EIT](#)) to create a fund supporting teachers who undertake innovative educational projects;
7. Recommends Member States to enhance group work quality and spontaneity promoting dancing and musical training courses in their educational curricula.

Sponsors

INSTITUTO PORTUGUÊS

DO **DESPORTO**

E **JUVENTUDE**, I. P.

EUROPEAN **YOUTH** PARLIAMENT
PORTUGAL